

**FACTORS BEHIND LOW ENGLISH SPEAKING ABILITY AMONG
ESL LEARNERS IN SRI LANKA; BASED GRADE 11 STUDENTS IN
TYPE-II SCHOOL IN COLOMBO, SRI LANKA.**

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Abstract: *This study aimed to identify the factors that affect English-speaking proficiency of ESL learners in Sri Lanka who complete 13 years of language education before leaving school. Sri Lankan students typically start learning English at the age of 6 and continue for their entire school career, yet mastering the language remains a difficult feat. The analysis aims to identify the challenges students encounter while honing their speaking abilities. To conduct the study, a sample of 40 students (comprising both genders and aged 15-16 years) was chosen through a simple random sampling approach. Primary data was gathered using a questionnaire, and a selection of students from the group were interviewed at random. Additionally, the students were observed during their classroom engagements to obtain further insights. As per the research, students encounter various external challenges that impede their language-acquiring process. These include insufficient exposure, limited opportunities to practice English beyond the classroom, inadequate school facilities, and unfavorable economic conditions. Additionally, psychological factors such as fear, anxiety, and negative attitudes can also pose significant barriers. Inadequate teaching resources, flawed pedagogical approaches, and a scarcity of qualified instructors have further compounded these challenges.*

Keywords: *Speaking Proficiency, School Education, ESL Learners*

Research background

English is not just a language, but also a tool of power in many former colonial countries, including Sri Lanka. Non-native speakers of English have a great inclination to learn this powerful language, as it is considered a necessary life skill. In today's fast-moving world, the ability to speak fluently and confidently in English is essential for many opportunities that lie ahead. If you are fluent in speaking English, you become a respectable person with knowledge of the world outside. The ability to converse in English has become the single most important requirement in many fields.

English is introduced in primary schools in Sri Lanka at the age of nine and is taught until grade 13. However, a significant number of students leave school without being able to speak English fluently. Even after years of struggling with the language, many students still find it challenging to

communicate comfortably in English. This is a sad reality in Sri Lanka.

Learning English isn't as easy as one may think. It's a skill that requires practice, and researchers and teachers acknowledge that becoming fluent in speaking English is a complex process. Despite many efforts to aid English language acquisition, many students still struggle to attain the expected level of fluency due to various challenges that hinder the learning process.

Structure of the education system

In Sri Lanka, children begin their formal schooling at the age of six. However, before this, parents provide preschool education to their children starting from the age of 2.5 years. The formal education system in Sri Lanka is administered by the government, semi-government, and private educational institutions. Government schools, semi-government schools, and private schools follow the national curriculum, while international schools follow either the Edexcel or the Cambridge curriculum. Nowadays, some private and international schools offer both national and Edexcel or Cambridge curriculums. The education system is divided into six stages: Nursery, Lower Nursery, Upper Nursery, Primary, Secondary, and Tertiary.

Table 1

Types	Classes/Grades in each type of school
1AB	Schools with classes up to Advanced Level (A/L) in all streams including Science (1AB schools have a sub-category called the National Schools)
1C	Schools with classes up to Advanced Level (A/L) in Arts and Commerce
II	Schools with classes from Grade One to Grade Eleven Ordinary Level (O/L)
III	Primary schools from Grade One to Five (some schools include Grades Six, Seven and Eight)

(Main Data and Indicators of Education, 2004)

The categorization of schools is based on the facilities available to the students. The difference in resources in a school can directly and indirectly affect the academic performance of its students. As government schools are free of charge, they are more attractive to parents from lower economic backgrounds. However, National schools are not easily accessible, no matter what is said. This creates high competition to get into National schools, and the leading ones are in very high demand.

Private or semi-government schools typically have students from better social backgrounds, as they charge a term or monthly fee. The top schools

among them demand higher school and admission fees, making them only approachable to the affluent in society. This exclusivity makes them more desirable for the top layer of social classes.

A majority of the international schools and fully private schools are located in the Colombo district. This is a fine indication of the financial capabilities and social background of the influential parents in the area. Out of all the districts, Colombo is regarded as the heart of the country. Being the commercial capital of the country it plays a major role in many sectors

Province	Medium of study			
Western	Sinhala	Tamil	English	Total
	859,982	79,891	25,240	965,113

Table 4 Students by the medium of study and province

When we take a close look at the statistics we see that even in Western provinces a majority of students learn in their mother tongue (L1). The number of students who are learning in English medium is very low. This is where we see the language difference very clearly. Those who are fluent enough to carry their studies in the English language are limited even in the Western province.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Research done on the Literature related to the factors affecting students acquiring the ability to converse in English after 11 years of schooling is available and easy to access. For this project research done on other relevant fields of English in Sri Lanka as well as research done in different parts of the world on topics relevant to this was analyzed. In the event of publication of this research, it would become useful for many in the field of education and other fields related to it. Namely, teachers – to make their teaching more effective by having a better understanding of the situation and to introduce a new methodology, textbook planners to scrutinize and make necessary alterations to make them more effective, and curriculum planners to re-evaluate their work as well as future researchers

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Karunaratne (28th - 30th November 2003) even in the urban areas teachers and students both depend heavily on the mother tongue. Sometimes teachers use L1 to clarify things and we have seen students responding using L1 to questions as well. “English is taught as the subject, not as the language” (Teevno, 2011). This is the biggest issue faced by the students in our country. They lack the confidence to use it outside their safe zone. All these factors together show the reasons behind why students even after 11 years of learning find it hard to converse in English. Their main goal is to perform well on the

GCE O/L exam with fine grades, even the teachers aim this and fill them with what they need for the written paper. But if even the child with 9 'A' grades does not have the confidence the fluency can bring to converse in English we have failed as Teachers of English in this country

Many language learners regard speaking ability as the measure of knowing a language. These learners define fluency as the ability to converse with others, much more than the ability to read, write, or comprehend oral language. They regard speaking as the most important skill they can acquire, and they assess their progress in terms of their accomplishments in spoken communication. (Factors Affecting English Speaking, 2011)

According to (Efrizal, 2012) speaking is of great importance for communication among people. It is a way of exchanging ideas and messages. If we want to encourage students to communicate in English, we should use the language in real-life situations and ask them to do the same as well.

It is not enough for a student just to have good writing skills and an extensive knowledge of the English language. To succeed in the society, the student must also be able to converse in English effectively. If a student lacks confidence in their language abilities, they will struggle to apply what they have learned in real-life situations. Speaking is an essential part of human interaction and communication. One should be able to use English words and phrases freely and fluently without being overly self-conscious. According to Vygotsky, learning occurs through social interaction and language. Language enables a person to share their experiences with others, while a lack of language skills can lead to isolation. Similarly, a lack of social interaction can hinder a student's learning process. This emphasizes the importance of language in our lives.

Fluency is defined by Huges (2002) as the ability to communicate without causing any breakdown in the conversation. It is important to keep the listener interested. Hedge (2000), on the other hand, defines fluency as the ability to connect words and phrases logically. This requires precise pronunciation, correct stress, and intonation patterns. Therefore, knowledge of language rules is essential.

Accuracy is a crucial characteristic of speech that language learners must pay close attention to. They need to focus on grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation while learning a language. Research by Thornbury (2005) shows that learners tend to pay less attention to pronunciation. However, for English, it is essential to have a solid understanding of phonological rules, stress patterns, intonations, and pitches. Learners should also be aware of the different sounds and how they are pronounced.

In a classroom, students of varying abilities may experience anxiety when presenting or speaking out. Strong learners may dominate the class, while weaker students may be ignored. Weak students often remain silent in the classroom due to a lack of confidence in their speaking ability. It's a well-known fact that individuals take steps to protect their fragile egos. As making errors in public can be perceived as a threat to one's ego, learners would rather stay silent than be shamed in front of others (Abeyseena, H., & Abeywickrama, R. (2020a).

METHOD

A mixed-methods research approach was used in a study to collect data on the challenges faced by students in acquiring spoken language proficiency. Two data collection instruments were used, including a questionnaire that allowed students to write about their specific issues. Quantitative analysis was conducted to understand the main challenges, while qualitative analysis was used to identify individual challenges faced by each student in mastering the spoken English component of the language. The study was conducted in an urban school that attracted students from diverse backgrounds, with the assumption that all social classes were represented. The research was carried out over two consecutive days in the third term of 2019, specifically in October.

RESEARCH SAMPLE

The research was conducted on a group of 28 students, consisting of 14 girls and 14 boys, who were between 15 and 16 years of age. The students belonged to different social classes, with some coming from low-income families and having no exposure to spoken English, while others came from English-speaking backgrounds. There were also disparities in their financial and family backgrounds. However, all the students were from the Sinhala ethnic group, and they were selected using a simple random sampling system.

The school selected for the research was a government school that, while not a National school or one of the leading schools, had attracted both lower-income and middle-class families in the neighborhood. It was located near one of the main cities in the Colombo District and had a student population of 1700, making it quite popular in the area. However, as it was highly urbanized, there were many shanties and lower-income groups around the school, and the children attending the selected school came from those areas.

THE FINDINGS

The type of school attended by the students

The students attending prestigious/private/national/international schools are likely to perform well in the English language. Their acquisition of language is of a higher level than that of other students as they have better exposure to the

language. The other factor is, that these prestigious schools have better access to language learning facilities and have the cream of qualified English teachers. Most of these schools attract students from the English speaking backgrounds creating a positive environment for better language acquisition inside the schools. The type II schools generally attract the less privileged in the society. The government schools being toll-free is one attraction, the neighborhood concept usually brings the same social class together into the schools. This would create an environment inside the school that could harm L2 acquisition.

LACK OF MOTIVATION AMONG STUDENTS

Dhanapala, R. M. (2021), emphasized the fact that there is a correlation with positive action and reaction between students' motivation and performance. The socio-economic problems in society and small schools make it difficult to attract the best teachers. The teachers appointed to these schools often do not work to their full potential as they believe that students and parents are not interested in English education. Insufficient materials for proper language teaching, Poor infrastructure in schools, Little or no exposure to the English language, Low income of parents and Lack of encouragement from parents due to their lack of understanding of the importance of English are some of the top ranking factors influence learners' motivation.

These factors demotivate students, who may not show interest in acquiring the English language. They may believe that they are unable to learn or use it and therefore it is of no use to them. The student's attitude towards their future job prospects also affects their motivation to learn to speak English, Abeywickrama, R. (2008). Some have already decided to follow in their parent's footsteps and do not have high hopes of being gainfully employed.

Most students in the lower social level are not motivated to do better than their parents. Only a small number of students are trying hard to acquire the ability to speak English, but they rarely get the support they need from school or parents. The general education system of the country values written exams, which harms spoken English. The speaking ability of the child is not tested or recognized anywhere, so teachers prioritize completing the syllabus and getting students to perform well on exams.

Especially in Grades 10 and eleven, higher attention is given to the written work and teaching of grammar. Mother tongue is often used to teach grammar in classes, and role plays and other speaking activities are ignored to make time for writing activities. This prevents students who do not speak English at home from seeing the practical use of the language.

Many teachers come from social backgrounds with less familiarity with

the English language, which results in a lack of proficiency in handling the spoken component of the language. Students and teachers may rely on their mother tongue in the language classroom, which impairs the oral interaction in the target language necessary for its acquisition. Since most of these students do not get any exposure to English outside the classroom, they miss the opportunity to see how the language is used authentically and may be exposed to wrong pronunciation and stress patterns. Parents' attitudes towards the English language also directly influence their children's attitudes.

Socio-economic status of parents

The poor social background of students is a significant factor that negatively affects their ability to speak English fluently. This creates a psychological barrier that discourages students from responding positively towards acquiring the language. This could be due to negative thinking patterns instilled in them by parents or their environment. Many learners from disadvantaged backgrounds lack exposure to real language use and are not familiar with even the most basic words or their proper pronunciation. Parents are often unable to provide the necessary support their children need to acquire the language, and creating an environment that encourages the use of English is not possible for them. Even those who want to help their children improve their English do not have the financial means to do so. Private tuition classes mainly focus on the school syllabus, and the institutes that help develop English-speaking skills are very costly. As this is not tested in national examinations, parents often prioritize tuition classes that cover the syllabus over spoken English institutes. Elocution courses, which are limited to the wealthy and influential, have not yet found their way to less privileged social sectors. The lack of understanding among Sri Lankan parents about the importance of learning to speak English better is a significant disadvantage for many students. Many do not speak any English at all and have a negative attitude towards the language, which hinders their ability to learn it. The courses offered by reputable institutes like the British Council or English Academy are not affordable for many poor parents.

LACK OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE EXPOSURE

Exposure to language is a crucial factor for learners to effectively learn a language. In Sri Lanka, students may receive better English language input in their classrooms, but once they step outside, they are mostly in a non-English speaking environment. Many Sri Lankan students from lower and middle socio-economic backgrounds do not use English for communication outside of their classrooms. They may not even get the opportunity to practice what they learn in

a social setting. Children living in and around lower-income areas do not have an English-speaking environment at home or in their surroundings. However, some bilingual students from better economic backgrounds have a good command of English. This is mainly due to their exposure to the language, as many of them communicate with family members in English. Although these students have access to media to some extent, such as television, they are not interested in following English language programs. They find it challenging to understand programs such as the English news of local channels or even the BBC. Additionally, they do not have the opportunity to use English outside the classroom, as Sinhala is sufficient to fulfill their needs. This poses a significant challenge for English language learners in Sri Lanka. On top of everything, Abeysena, H., & Abeywickrama, R. (2020), unveiled the fact that shaming practice are less addressed during the course of lesson and this also hamper learners' exposure to practice English in their classroom.

LACK OF ACCESS TO DIFFERENTIATED LEARNING MATERIALS

The government has printed a common English text and workbook to provide equal learning opportunities for all students. However, the materials have not taken into account the different abilities of the learners. Students with lower language abilities struggle with the book, while advanced students find it boring due to the lack of challenge. Those from English-speaking backgrounds also find it too easy, while those who do not speak English outside of the classroom find it too difficult and become discouraged. Teachers in mixed-level classrooms struggle to cater to both groups.

Although the English textbook prepares students for written exams, it does not encourage speaking ability. An activity book was introduced to encourage speaking ability, but teachers are more focused on covering the syllabus and preparing students for written exams, resulting in the activity book being underutilized.

OVERCROWDED CLASSROOMS

One of the biggest demotivating factors for English teachers in Sri Lanka is the issue of overcrowded classrooms. In Sri Lanka, a typical classroom consists of around 30 to 40 students, but in some areas, it can be as high as 50 students per class. This results in teachers struggling to provide quality education and a positive learning environment for their students. Small class sizes, on the other hand, help to reduce discipline issues, enable teachers to identify problems immediately, and provide individual support to students. They also provide ample time to cover the syllabus. In a small class, the teacher can give close attention to each student and provide individual support, making it

easier to identify learning problems or avoid unnecessary issues of discipline.

SPEAKING IS COMPLETELY IGNORED IN THE CLASSROOM

As speaking is not a skill tested at any national exam this has become the most neglected area in Sri Lanka. No one pays real attention to developing the speaking ability of the students. Many say that English is not spoken by them or the teacher even during their English period. This is the main reason why the skill of speaking is not developed in the country.

LINGUISTIC CHALLENGES

Every language has its unique language structure, and one should not attempt to apply the structure of one language to another. This is known as direct translation, and it often results in grammatically incorrect sentences. For example, English has an SVO (Subject-Verb-Object) structure, while Sinhala has an SOV (Subject-Object-Verb) structure. However, some students attempt direct translations between the two languages, which demonstrates a lack of knowledge of grammar and language structure. This affects the students' speaking ability directly.

For instance, the Sinhala sentence "Mama pasalata yami" translates to "I am going to school" in English. However, a direct translation would result in "I school go", which is grammatically incorrect.

It is not easy to learn a second language, and if a student becomes accustomed to thinking in their mother tongue first and then translating it into their second language, it could create problems. Additionally, the pronunciation and stress patterns of the second language could be affected by the student's mother tongue influence. Moreover, Arshad, S. M. B. M. (2023) emphasized the fact that teachers should follow different methods and techniques to increase vocabularies, which is one of another important problems.

FEAR AND ANXIETY

These two are psychological factors that affect the language learning ability of a student. The lack of self-confidence could result from it as well as previous bad experiences. Lack of practice in the use of language can also bring anxiety to a person. The fear of being ridiculed, laughed at for mistakes or the inferiority complex could create this situation in a student. The best way to handle it would be to practice to build confidence in his or her ability.

CONCLUSION

Learning a second language is a challenging task. Despite the popularity of English in Sri Lankan education, many students struggle to master it. Although some assume that learning English is easy, it requires a lot of effort. The free education policy introduced by Dr. C. W. W. Kannangara aimed to

create equal opportunities for all, but it has not been successful in achieving its goals. There are many discrepancies in the field of education, particularly in teaching English as a second language. It is now imperative to find solutions to these problems to improve the English-speaking ability of our students. If a child who has been studying English for 8-10 years since grade 3 is still unable to converse fluently, then our education system has failed. Lack of facilities and exposure to the language are the primary challenges that need to be addressed immediately. Additionally, the socio-economic status of parents is another area that requires attention. The lack of properly trained teachers to teach the language has also harmed education. Once these key problems are addressed, the language-speaking ability of our students will improve significantly.

REFERENCES

1. Abeysena, H., & Abeywickrama, R. (2020). Linguistic shame and shaming: Teacher educator awareness and English language teacher education in Sri Lanka. In *ICERI2020 Proceedings* (pp. 5802-5810). IATED.
2. Abeysena, H., & Abeywickrama, R. (2020a). Linguistic shame and shaming: Teacher educator awareness and English language teacher education in Sri Lanka. In *ICERI2020 Proceedings* (pp. 5802-5810). IATED.
3. Abeywickrama, R. (2008). Research on Attitudes of Students to the GCE General English Course with Special Emphasis on Schools of the Balangoda Educational Zone, Sri Lanka.
4. Ali, M. (2019, September 19). 10+ problems faced by teachers in teaching the English Language. Retrieved from di blogger: diblogger.com/problems-faced-teachers-teaching-english-language
5. Arshad, S. M. B. M. (2023). EFFECTIVE TECHNIQUES FOR EFL TEACHERS AND LEARNERS TO INCREASE BEGINNER'S LEVEL VOCABULARY. *Science and innovation*, 2(B12), 19-27.
6. Bashir, M., Azeem, M., & Dogar, A. H. (2011). Factor effecting students' English speaking skills. *British journal of arts and social sciences*, 2(1), 34-50.
7. Dhanapala, R. M. (2021). The effect of learning environment on academic performance from students' perspective. *Global Scientific Journal*, 9 (3).
8. Efrizal, D. (2012). Improving students' speaking through communicative language teaching method at Mts Ja-alhaq, Sentot Ali Basa Islamic boarding school of Bengkulu, Indonesia. *International Journal of Humanities and social science*, 2(20), 127-134.
9. Factors affecting English speaking. (2011). *British Journal of Arts and Social Science*, 2. Retrieved from <http://www.bjournal.co.uk/BJASS.asp>
10. Hedge, T. (2001). *Teaching and learning in the language classroom* (Vol.

- 106). Oxford, UK: Oxford university press.
11. Huges, R. (2002). Teaching and researching speaking. Harlow CM20 2JE: PEARSON EDUCATION LIMITED.
12. Hughes, C., & Graham, A. (2002). Measuring executive functions in childhood: Problems and solutions?. *Child and adolescent mental health*, 7(3), 131-142.
13. Karunaratne, I. M. (28th - 30th November 2003). International Conference on Sri Lanka studies-teaching English in Urban Sri Lanka. 9th International Conference on Sri Lanka Studies. Matara - Sri Lanka. Retrieved from <https://slidex.tips/download/teaching-english-in-urban-sri-lanka-some-pedagogical-issues-iresha-madhavi-karun>
14. Krashen, S. (1992). The input hypothesis: An update. *Linguistics and language pedagogy: The state of the art*, 409-431.
15. Mai, N. H. (2015). FACTORS AFFECTING STUDENTS' SPEAKING PERFORMANCE AT LE. *Asian Journal of Educational Research*, 8 to 18.
16. Teevno, Roshan Ali (2011). Challenges in Teaching and Learning of English at Secondary Level class X. Research Paper: *International Journal of Human Resource Studies* 1.2 : (pp. 27-34).
17. Thornbury, S. (2005). *How to teach speaking*. Longman.
18. ТОМЧИЛАТИБ СУҒОРИШ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИ ОРҚАЛИ СУҒОРИЛГАН ОЛМА БОҒЛАРИНИНГ ТУПРОҚ АГРОКИМЁВИЙ КЎРСАТГИЧЛАРИ. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Educational Discoveries and Humanities* (Vol. 2, No. 11, pp. 19-23).
19. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш. (2019). EFFICIENCY OF USE OF CLAY WATER WITH DROP IRRIGATION. *ЖУРНАЛ АГРО ПРОЦЕССИНГ*, (4).
20. Xudayev, I. J., & Tojiyev, S. M. (2023). NAMLATGICH-BLOKLARDAN HOSIL QILINGAN EKTRANLI EGATLARDAN G 'O 'ZANI SUG 'ORISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. In *Uz-Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 514-519).